

ERC AdG Locus Ludi. The Cultural Fabric of Play and Games in Classical Antiquity (741520)

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Session Games, Fate and chance

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Afrodite che gioca agli astragali: oracoli erotici e invocazioni a Venere nell'astragalomanzia

This contribution explores the inextricable connections between oracles drawn by throwing astragali and love prophecies, well documented in the Roman Imperial times. Love stories very regularly recur as a key theme among divinatory answers submitted to a supernatural rationality beyond the chance of normal human mind. Astragali, dice and similar tools are conceived as useful random-givers in the realm of affairs of the heart that are seemingly beyond understanding. Therefore, I intend to analyze invocations addressed to Aphrodite in astragalomantic predictions, as well as love answers given in this specimen of Graeco-Roman divination, in order to better define the profile of the inquirers respectively authors of these *astragalomanteia*. Prayers are, here, to be addressed to different *epicleseis* of the Love-goddess, who really plays with astragales, as Gabriele d'Annunzio states in his *Fedra* speaking of two major concepts of chance, such as dice' throw and love.

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Games, Fate and Chance

This paper will explore the relation of games with tuchê, fortune, as suggested by the offering of Palamedes in the temple of the goddess in Argos. It will present a large range of personal devices (rings, pendants...) where game devices, such as dice and knucklebones, and the representation of play, are most likely used to secure luck to their wearers.

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Playing with fate: horoscope on engraved gemstones

Fate (*heimarmene*) is always present in astrological treatises. It is well known that at the time of birth the stars fix the destiny of the newborn. Since the studies of Franz Cumont, fate in Graeco-Roman times is associated to the impossibility to change it. Astral fatalism claims that no one can undo what is already written in the stars.

The representation of a personal horoscope as well as the one of a famous person like an emperor, is found on different media (icosahedron, rings and engraved gemstones), and seems to point in a different direction, namely the will to metaphorically play with one's own destiny in order to change it. A series of astrological texts that are contemporary to this type of horoscope (2nd and 3rd

century A.D.) display the desire to possess a personal birth chart in order to change one's fate and attract luck. Some magical formulae and rituals seems to be able to "change the clothes of destiny", (Berlin's Papyrus 10525, Prayer to Sarapis, 2nd century A.D.).

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« *Preso per i capelli* »: un'indagine su *kairos* e la fortuna in Grecia / « *Pris par les cheveux* » : une enquête sur *kairos* et la fortune en Grèce ancienne

Dans le cadre du projet ERC 'Locus ludi' qui vise à établir une attention nouvelle à la culture ludique de l'Antiquité gréco-romaine en faisant recours à une approche anthropologique et historique cette intervention abordera le rapport entre hasard, fortune et chance à partir du dossier de textes concernant le terme grec *kairos*.

Cette catégorie bien particulière qui ne recoupe pas totalement la notion moderne de hasard ni celle de chance est bien différente aussi d'autres termes qui en grec ancien lui sembleraient liés tels que *tuchē* ou *charis*.

En analysant les textes qui associent le terme *kairos* aux contextes ludiques et plus spécifiquement agonistiques on cherchera à fournir un portrait-robot le plus détaillé possible de cette catégorie qui était pour les Anciens, il ne faut pas l'oublier, avant tout un dieu, considéré fils de Zeus.

Une attention particulière sera consacrée aussi aux aspects iconographiques et aux sources qui nous décrivent les traits les plus saillants de sa figure divine, en particulier on se concentrera sur le célèbre épigramme de Posidippe (275 *AnthPal* = 142 Austin Bastianini) qui décrit le rôle de premier plan joué par les cheveux du dieu dans l'imaginaire antique concernant *kairos*.